

The Jain Heritage of Odisha

-Arpit Shah

Enriched with forests, waterfalls, rivers, valleys, beaches, lakes and temples, Odisha is a kaleidoscope of past splendor and present glory. Being the meeting place of Aryan and Dravidian cultures, with its delightful assimilations, from the fascinating lifestyle of the tribes, Odisha retains in its distinct identity. **Once, a stronghold of Jainism, the Jain heritage of Odisha has now been lost in the pages of history.** Such was the dominant presence of Jainism in the ancient era, that a Vedic Puran named “*Adityapuram*” placed Kalinga in the list of “*Anarya Bhumis*”[\[1\]](#) (a land where the Dharma is not established), whereas Jains gave Kalinga, a place in its list of 25 *Arya Bhumis* (where Dharma was established).

Following is the timeline of Jainism in Odisha -

~850 BC - The revered Jain Agam, **Shri Uttaradhyayan Sutra** mentions that **Lord Parshwanath visited this region in 850 BC** when the King Avakinnayo **Karakandu** became a great devotee of the 23rd Tirthankar and took *Diksha* (monkhood)[\[2\]](#). *Jain KshetraSamsa* as well as Jain texts like *VyavaharBhashya* and *HarivashPuran* also show that Lord Parshwanath had preached in places like **Tamralipti** (Tamluk in West Bengal), **Kopataka** (Kupari, Balasore) and **KumariParvat** (Udaygiri and Khandgiri, Bhubaneshwar) in the Kalinga region[\[3\]](#). Therefore, as early as 9th century B.C, Jainism had already created its place in the religious life of the people of Odisha, and continued to flourish under the royal patronage.

558 BC - As per Jain scriptures like *Shri Bhagwati Sutra*, *Shri Avashyak (Niryukti) Sutra*, *HarivanshPuran* and *Haribhadravritti*, **Lord Mahavir visited various places like** Valuyagam, Subhoma, Succheta Malaya, Siddharthgram and **Tosali** (Sisupalgarh, Bhubaneshwar) in Kalinga after 11 years of *Diksha* with MankhaliputraGoshal[\[4\]](#) [\[5\]](#).

~ 530 -510 BC - Emperor **Shrenik** Bimbisar of the Magadh empire, who was a great devotee of Lord Mahavir made a pilgrimage to **KumariParvat** (Udaygiri and Khandgiri, Bhubaneshwar) and constructed a beautiful temple on the hill and placed a golden idol of Lord Adinath which was installed by **GandharSudharma Swami**. This idol came to be known as the “**Kalinga Jina**” and was deeply revered by the entire populace of Kalinga. King Shrenik also constructed rock cut caves in Kumargiri for the use of Jain monks and nuns during monsoon[\[6\]](#) [\[7\]](#).

509 BC / 468 BC - King Chetak who was the maternal uncle of Lord Mahavir, ruled over Vaishali in 5th century BC. His son, **Shobhanraya** was married to Kalinga emperor Sulochan’s daughter. After Chetak lost Vaishali to KonikAjatshatru, Shobhanraya fled to Kalinga. As Sulochan had no sons,

Shobhanray was crowned the ruler of Kalinga. Shobhanraya was a staunch Jain and during his rule Jainism flourished making KumariParvat a major pilgrimage[8].

378 BC - Chandaraya was crowned as the 5th successor of Shobhanraya. During that time, **the 8th Nanda emperor Kaivarta Nanda attacked the kingdom of Kalinga**, destroyed the temple on KumariParvat **and took away the idol of Kalinga Jina** to Patliputra[9].

357 BC - HimavantSthaviravali by Acharya

HimavantKshamashraman (composed in ~2-3rd century AD) states that the last Purvadhara, (i.e. who had the knowledge of all the 14 Purvas) **Acharya Bhadrabahu Swami arrived in KumariParvat**, 170 years after the nirvan of Mahavir. **He attained Kaldharma (death) through an Anshan** (meditative penance known as Santhara/ Sallekhana) of 15 days of fasting without even consuming water[10].

282 BC – Arya Mahagiri arrived in KumariParvat and attained Kaldharma by practicing Anshan[11]

265 BC - Emperor Ashok Maurya attacked the Kalinga empire and annexed it to the Mauryan empire.

236 BC - Arya Suhastisuri (guru of Emperor Samprati) arrived in KumariParvat and attained Kaldharma by practicing Anshan[12]

232 BC – Kalinga regained independence from Mauryan empire post Ashoka's death[13]. Kalinga's ruler, **Vudharaja** (Vridharaja) **built 11 caves** on KumariParvat for the use of Jain monks and nuns during monsoon[14].

Udaygiri Caves (Source: Wikimedia Commons)

165 BC – Vudharaja’s son, **MahameghvanBhikhshurajKharavel** ascended to the throne of Kalinga[15].

157 BC – **Kharavel attacked and defeated Magadha**, which was then ruled by Bahasatimita or Pushyamitra of the Shunga dynasty **and recovered the idol of Kalinga Jina** which was captured by the Nandas[16].

156 BC –The temple on KumariParvat was renovated and the **idol of Kalinga Jina was reinstalled** in the presence of **Arya Shri Susthitsuri** and **Achrya Shri Supratibuddhsuri**[17]. Both the Acharyas conducted one crore chants of the holy “Suri Mantra” there.[18]

Image of the Apsidal Chaitya structure at Udaygiri where the Kalinga Jina was installed

Top view of the Apsidal Chaitya structure at Udaygiri

To preserve the knowledge of Jain Agams, **Kharavel initiated an AgamVanchana (council) for a verbal compilation of the Agams and especially the Purvas (Drishtivad)**. Kharavel invited Acharya Balissah, Acharya Bodhiling, Devacharya, Acharya Dharmasena, Acharya Nakshatra along with 200 Jinakalpi monks (naked monks who used to imitate the life and penances of Tirthankars as per Shwetambar Agams; now extinct.) and Sthavirakalpi Acharyas (Cloth bearer monks) namely Arya Susthitsuri, Acharya Supratibuddhsuri, Acharya Umasvati, Acharya Shyamacharya along with 300 Sthavirakalpi monks. Arya Poini along with 300 nuns and 700 Shravaks- Shravikas were also present during the compilation [19].

Based on the compilation, **following scriptures were composed** later [20] [21]–

- “*Pragnapana Sutra*” (Pannavana) by Arya Shri Shyamacharya
- “*Angavidya Sutra*” (from a Purva named Vidyaprasad) by Arya Shri Balissah
- “*Tattvartha Sutra*” by Acharya Umasvati.

Kharavel also **constructed rock cut cave shelters** for Jain monks on both the hills of Kumari Parvat (Udaygiri and Khandgiri). On one hill, he constructed caves for Jinakalpi monks (Udaygiri) and on the other he constructed caves for the Sthavirakalpi monks (Khandgiri) [22].

152 BC – The **Hathigumpha inscription** was carved on the Kumari Parvat (Udaygiri) which mentions the life of Kharavel in Prakrit. The inscription begins with the words [23] – “*Namo Arhantanam, NamoSavasidhanam*” making it the earliest archaeological evidence of Navkar mantra. Other important highlights of the inscription are –

- In the 8th year of his reign, Kharavel expelled members of the Ajivika sect (followers of Makkhali Gosala) from the Barabar caves in Gaya and mutilated their inscriptions [24] [25].
- In the 12th year of his reign, Kharavela caused panic amongst the people of Magadha by driving (his) elephants into the Sugamgiya (Palace), made the King of Magadha, Bahasatimita, bow at his feet and **recovered (the image) 'the Jina of Kalinga'** which had been taken away by King Nanda [26] [27] [28].
- In the 13th year of his reign, on the Kumari Hill where the Wheel of Conquest had been well-revolved (i.e., the religion of Jina had been preached), **he offered respectfully royal maintenances, silks and white clothes to the Jain monks who by their austerities had extinguished the round of lives**. As a layman, Kharavel realised the nature of “jiva” and

“deha” and brought a Council of the wise Jain ascetics and sages, from hundred (i.e., all) quarters near the temple of Kalinga Jina on the top of the hill, with stones brought from many miles (yojanas). He restored and renovated the Arhat temple on the Kumari Hill by spending twenty-five hundred thousands; and caused to be compiled expeditiously the (text) of the seven-fold Angas (Jain Agams)[\[29\]](#)

The Hathigumpha inscription

~150 BC – Maharaja **Kudepasiri** succeeded Kharavel as the ruler of Kalinga[\[30\]](#). He also built caves for Jain monks on KumariParvat. Inscriptions in the Manchapuri cave in the KumariParvat (Udaygiri) mentions his name[\[31\]](#). **The cave also depicts a relief representing two male figures and two female figures worshipping the Kalinga Jina**[\[32\]](#).

Relief in Manchapuri Cave depicting the worship of Kalinga Jina (Source: Wikimedia Commons)

40 AD -50 AD – Due to an acute famine in northern India, Acharya Vajraswami (who had the knowledge of the 10 purvas) arrived at the coastal town of Puri[33] where there was a Jain temple dedicated to Shri JirawalaParshwanath[34]. He also successfully made the local Buddhist king embrace Jainism. Currently a Jain idol can be seen on the outer walls of the JagannathPuri Temple.

Stories by Arpit JAIN IMAGES AT SHRI JAGANNATH TEMPLE, PURI

A Tirthanakar idol on the outer walls of Jagannath Temple, Puri. Even the tradition of erecting Manstambh outside the temple (which is known as Arun Stambh in front of Singhdwar of Jagannath Temple) is typical of Jains.

Stories by Arpit

जगन्नाथ की विविध पहचान

मायथोलॉजी
देवदत्त पटनायक
राष्ट्रीय पारंपरिक धर्मशास्त्र के अध्येताओं और लेखक

क्या वहाँ के अन्य धार्मिकों को कुछ रजत था। उनको और भी कई पहचानें थीं। तो सबसे पहचान फैन-नो समझी क्यों?

इस ले में ओडिशा के जगन्नाथ मंदिर में मुझे ऐसे ही अमूर्तता का सामना करना पड़ा। मुझे लगता था कि कुम्भ के स्वर्ण स्वर्ण का ही जगन्नाथ के रूप में धारणा मिली। फिर किसी ने मुझे बताया कि लक्ष्मी उनकी सार्वभौमिक हैं और इतिहास ने विष्णु का भी स्वरूप है। कुछ संसारों में कुम्भ 'केवल' विष्णु के अकार है, जबकि अन्य संसारों में कुम्भ को विष्णु से सर्वोच्च मान गण्य है। फिर कई लोगों ने मुझे बताया कि ओडिशा में जगन्नाथ अद्वितीय है। उन पर कुम्भ और विष्णु जैसी पहचानें तो कार: जैन तीर्थंकर की मुर्तियाँ हैं। क्या यह मुझे साध्य की है, जिसे धर्मार्थ पूजा में कुम्भ का रूप माना गया है? या क्या यह इस राक्षे की यह दिशा है कि जगन्नाथ मंदिर की

जगन्नाथ मंदिर में मुझे भी? दूसरी कहानी के अनुसार जगन्नाथ की प्रतीक के अंतर बुद्ध के अवरोध रचें हुए हैं, जिस कारण ने एक बौद्ध देवता बन जाने हैं। इस कहानी को हमारा नहीं किया जा सकता, लेकिन मंदिर के कई हिस्सों में जगन्नाथ की प्रतिमाएं दशकला की प्रतिमाओं में जैसे रूप में दिखाई देती हैं। जयदेव ने अपना 'पंच शोभित' इसी मंदिर के परिसर में रचा था। उसके पंच आज तक मंदिर की राखी का हिस्सा है। यह संभव है कि विष्णु के दशकला की सूची, जिसमें बुद्ध नहीं अस्वात थे, जयदेव ने प्रस्तावित की। इस सूची और प्रतिमाओं के अकार पर कई लोग मानते हैं कि जगन्नाथ बौद्ध धर्म से जुड़े होंगे। लेकिन इस ले में लोगों ने इस 'बौद्ध' पहचान को सुनने से रोना शुरू कर दिया है कि जगन्नाथ 'अज्ञात' कैसे हो सकते हैं?

अतः, जैन धार्मिकों का खयाल है कि मंदिर में प्रतिमाएं अज्ञात में तीन शीघ्र हैं। इस कारण वे प्रतिमाएं कुम्भ और उनके धर्म-संबंध को नहीं हैं, बल्कि विश्व के ही तीन रूप हैं। राक्षसों का खयाल है कि वे प्रतिमाएं देवी की हैं।

कहावली राज विष्णुवध, 'नैलगायध' को पुराने थे। राज इंद्रधनु ने भी नैलगायध को अपना लिया।

इंद्रधनु ने वीरगन मंदिर में बहुत पहले ही भगवान जगन्नाथ का पहला मंदिर बनवाया था। इस तरह एक अन्य धारा के अनुसार जगन्नाथ की पहचान अतिरिक्त ब्रह्मवर्ती देवता के रूप में भी स्थापित होती है। इतिहास मंदिर में कई पुराने 'देव-पति' हैं और उनका खोज कर्मियों ने है। वे जगन्नाथ पदाओं से विस्तृत आता है।

विद्वानों ने इस बात को लेकर विचार है कि जब जगन्नाथ मंदिर की पांचा हिंदू या बौद्ध परंपरा में पहले शुरू हुए या बौद्ध परंपरा के बाद शुरू हुए थे। फिर यह बौद्ध परंपरा के समापन भी अज्ञात में थी। क्या यह हिंदू परंपराओं का खोज है या उनका फलन, क्या उसे पोषण, धर्म, परंपरा, संरक्षण या कल्प बनाने चाहिए? कस्तु शब्द का इस्तेमाल अक्षय्य सुरुवात और अमौलिक भारतीय विद्वान करते हैं और या संवेदनशील भारतीयों को कोषित करता है।

इस परमंत्र ओडिशा ओडिशा (पैअरॉन्) की पहचान को तरह है। उन राय कि जगन्नाथ में पहचान को लेकर तरह-तरह के स्थापित उठते रहते हैं। लेकिन शुरू है कि पैअरॉन् को मानता और जगन्नाथ को दिशा पर कोई साक्ष्य नहीं आता।

देवदत्त पटनायक

JagannathkiVividhPehchan by DevduttPattnaik

2nd Century - 3rd Century AD – A tribe called Murundas, who ruled over an extensive territory from Chota Nagpur region of Bihar to the district of Ganjam in Odisha patronized Jainism[35] [36]. Gold coins excavated from Sisupalgarh near Bhubaneswar show that MaharajadhirajaDharmadamadara who belonged to

the *Murunda* tribe was a patron of Jainism[37]. This fact is corroborated by the Jain text *PrabodhChintamani*. The last ruler of the Murunda tribe also practiced Jainism and worshipped the Nirgranth tradition (Jainism)[38]

Early 4th Century AD - Satrubhanja ruled from the Keonjhar district of Odisha and the **Asanpat inscription** from Keonjhar district states that he donated large amount of wealth to Bhikshus, **Nirgranth**s although he himself remained a staunch follower of Brahmanism[39].

7th Century AD – Buddhist traveler **Hiuen-T'sang**'s records state that Kalinga had 10 Buddhist Sangharamas (monasteries) with 100 priests and 500 temples with different sorts of unbelievers most of whom were Nirgranth (Jains)[40]. He adds that **Buddhist temples were about 100 in numbers whereas those of (Jain) Tirthankars were more than 1000**[41].

The Inscriptions of **Shailodbhava dynasty** who ruled over the Kangoda region (parts of the present-day Ganjam, Khordha and Puri districts in the Odisha state) inform that Jains followed extreme penance and austerity to attain supreme knowledge[42]. The Banapura copper plate records that Shailodbhava king Dharmaraja II alias Sri Manabhita's wife **Kalyandevi** was a Jain and **she made grants for Jain monks** namely Arhatacharya Nasichandra and his disciple EkasataPrabuddhachandra **who wore only one piece of cloth**[43].

10-11th Century AD – The **Somavamshi dynasty** gave royal patronage to Jainism and erected Jain temples at various places including Bhubaneswar[44]. King **Uddyotakeshari** of the Somavamshi dynasty **built cave temples and installed idols of 24 Tirthankars on the KumariParvat** (Khandgiri) as per the three inscriptions engraved inside the Lalatendukesari cave and Navamuni cave of the Khandagiri hill [45] [46].

12th Century AD – **Ganga dynasty** rose into power in Kalinga who were staunch followers of Vaishnavism. AnantavarmanChodaganga constructed the temple of Shri Jagannath at Puri. A **stone inscription**[47] from **Bhogpur** village (Bhimilipatnam Taluk of the Vishakhapatnam district) reveals that in 1178 A.D (11th regnal year of AnantavarmanRajaraja II of the Ganga dynasty) one **KannamNayak** (Sreshthi), a subordinate of the Utkal King, **installed a sacred image of Tirthankar at Ramaramagiri** (the modern Ramatirtham) in a temple called RajarajaJinalaya which is undoubtedly named after his overlord, Rajaraja II.

Thereafter, the presence of Jainism gradually declined in the region because of lack of royal patronage and intolerant attitude of other sects.

ARCHAEOLOGICAL EVIDENCES OF ANTIQUITY OF JAINISM IN ODISHA

Based on the documented resources available in Research papers, museum directories, historical publications and Archaeological newsletters, **I have been able to list more than 120 cities/ villages**[\[48\]](#) [\[49\]](#) [\[50\]](#) **where Jain archaeological remains** have been found within the state boundaries of Odisha. The entire list has been provided at the end of the article.

It is important to note that **the list is not exhaustive** and there could be various other sites as well. I have tried to sort them from north to south based on their districts and locations. **Out of the 30 districts in Odisha, Jain historical remains have been identified in 15 districts** in form of idols of Tirthankars, Yaksh/ Yakshini's, votive tablets etc. Five Districts namely Koraput, Jajpur, Balasore, Cuttack and Khordha account for more than 76% of the Jain historical remains.

While most of these idols are kept in Hindu temples and worshipped as Bhairav's, Gramdevata's, Devi's etc. some are well preserved in the museums in the state. **Sadly, animal sacrifices are offered in front of many idols which are worshipped as local deities.**

Mayurbhanj District

Major Jain archaeological sites can be found in the towns of **Baripada, Khiching** and **Badasahi** in Mayurbhanj district. The **Jagannath temple of Baripada** houses three Jain images out of which two images date back to the 9th century AD. The outer wall of **MaaKichakeswari Temple**, Khiching depict a relief showing a Jinakalpi Jain monk giving a sermon to a King/ prince. Jain images are also preserved in the Baripada state museum and Khiching museum.

Jain idols from Mayurbhanj District, Odisha

Keonjhar District

The most notable site in this district is **Podasingidi** where many Tirthankar idols have been excavated. Most of the idols are preserved in the Jain Heritage Sculpture Shed maintained by the ASI and Odisha State museum in Bhubaneswar date back to 7th to 12th century AD. Rare images of **Ambika with Tirthankars** are worshipped by locals at Ramchandi Temple in Podasingidi. The Baula hill in the Anandapur subdivision has a Jain temple known as Yogichhata. The hill also has rock cut caves, which were used by Jain monks.

Jain idols from Podasingidi, Keonjhar District, Odisha

Jain idols from Keonjhar District.

Balasure District

With the **third highest** number of Jain historical remains in the State of Odisha, **Balasure District** has 16 Jain sites. The **Narayan Temple** at the village

of **Ada** and the Archaeological shed at **Ajodhya** preserve most of the images. Sadly, the images at the Narayan temple lie in ruins, neglected completely.

Jain idols from Narayana Temple, Ada, Balasore District

Jain idols from Ajodhya, Balasore District

Puruna

Bhimpur

Balighat

Jain images at Gada Chandi Temple

Biswanath Temple

Kabara

Chaturmukhi Shrine, Nilagiri

Majhikia

Jain idols from Ajodhya, Balasore District

Bhadrak District

Although only three Jain sites have been identified in this District, the site of **Charampa** is a very significant one as many medieval era Jain idols were found from here. A colossal 6 feet high idol of Lord Adinath dating to the 9th century AD was excavated from Charampa along with **unique idols of Shri Ajitnath and Shri Shantinath Bhagwan bearing cut marks** which are kept at Odisha State museum, Bhubaneshwar. The double concave cut marks found on those idols indicate to votary of the faith of the extreme path followed by the Tirthankars to achieve salvation. These idols also have been assigned to the 8th and 9th centuries A.D. One idol of **Shri Parshwanath** is being worshipped as **Kharakia Thakurani** in the Charampa village by the locals.

Jain idols from Charampa, Bhadrak District

Jajpur&Kendrapada Districts

The Jajpur District has the **second highest number of Jain sites** across Odisha (23 to be precise). Major sites include **Jajpur town, Baruadi, Narasinghpur, Kantabania, Bansabadi, Kuansa** among others. At **Narayana Chowk**, Shri Parshwanath Bhagwan is worshipped as **Anant Vasudev** whereas an unidentified Tirthankar image is worshipped as **Vishnu in Narasinghpur**. The **Hanseshvar temple** and **Sitaleshvar temple** have many Jain idols in their custody. A **Chaturmukhi shrine** is used as a **base for a garden pot in Narasinghpur** while multiple Chaturmukhi shrines lie scattered in the fields of **Nayagarh**.

Stories by Aapit

JAIN IMAGES FROM JAJPUR DISTRICT - I

Hanseshvar Temple, Jajpur

Sitalashvar Temple, Jajpur

Baruadi

Shri Parshwanath worshipped as Anant Vasudev, Narayana Chowk

Sana Bazar, Jajpur

Stories by Aapit

Jain idols from Jajpur District

Stories by Aapit

JAIN IMAGES FROM JAJPUR DISTRICT - II

Dashashvamedh Ghat

Narasinghpur

Tirthankar image converted to a Vishnu image, Narasinghpur

Chaturmukhi shrine used as a base for garden pot, Narasinghpur

Kartar

Chandigola

Hatadiha

Kantabania

Taranga Sagarpur

Stories by Aapit

Jain idols from Jajpur District

Stories by Arpit

JAIN IMAGES FROM JAJPUR DISTRICT - III

Bansabadi

Champeipal

Sripura

Tendulidiha

Votive tablet depicting Tirthankar,
Gandhar and Purvadhhar, Kuansa

Madhupur

Naguan

Stories by Arpit

Jain idols from Jajpur District

Stories by Arpit

JAIN IMAGES FROM JAJPUR DISTRICT - IV

Ratnagiri, Jajpur

Kamudei Pitha

Chaturmukhi shrines lying ruined on the
fields, Nayagarh

Stories by Arpit

Jain idols from Jajpur District

Cuttack District

Scattered across 12 different cities/ towns, Jain sites across Cuttack District are very prominent. **Pratapnagari** near Cuttack preserves a maximum number of Jain idols and a small museum has been constructed on the site. While most of idols at **Choudwar** have been **badly painted and worshipped as Shiva, ParshwanathBhagwan** is worshipped as **Anantavasudeva** at **Bhanapur**. Cuttack has temples of both the Digambar and Shwetambar sect, but the **Digambar Jain temple** preserves very beautiful ancient idols dating back to 11th century AD. The walls and pillars of **Sobhaneshwar Temple, Niali** show images of Tirthankars in Kayotsarg mudra which suggest that this was a Jain temple in ancient times.

Jain idols from Cuttack District

Jain idols from Cuttack District

Jain idols from Pratapnagari, Cuttack District

Jain idols from Choudwar, Cuttack District

Jagatsinghpur District

Nuadhana, Sahada, Nasik are major sites in Jagatsinghpur district. A Jain idol in **Nuadhana** is worshipped as **Gramdevati** (village deity) and animal sacrifices are made in front of the idol.

Jain idols from Jagatsinghpur District

Khordha District

Blessed with the most important Jain center in the entire state of Odisha, **KumariParvat, (now known as Udaygiri and Khandagiri Caves)** the Khordha District has 12 Jain sites in its precincts. The town of **Sisupalgarh** near Bhubaneshwar was known as **Tosali** and was **visited by Shri Mahavir Swami** Bhagwan. Fragments of idols of Jain Tirthankars have been found from the walls of temples in Bhubaneshwar and the Odisha State Museum in the city preserves various Jain artefacts. A **clothed Tirthankar idol** can also be seen on the **outer walls of the Somnath Temple in Budhapada**. In **Panchagaon** a votive tablet depicting **Arhat, Gandhars&Purvadhars**, has been found.

Jain idols from Udaygiri - Khandagiri, Khordha District

Stories by Arpit JAIN IMAGES FROM BHUBANESHWAR, KHORDHA DISTRICT

Jain images from Bhubaneswar at Odisha State Museum

Tirthankar images on the pillars of Brahmeshwar Temple, Bhubaneswar

Stories by Arpit

Jain idols from Bhubaneswar, Khordha District

Stories by Arpit JAIN IMAGES FROM KHORDHA DISTRICT

Remains of a temple believed to house Kalinga Jina at some point of time at Tosali, Sisupalgarh

Panchagaon

Budhapada

Clothed Tirthankar idol at Budhapada, Somnath Temple

Votive tablet depicting Arhat, Gandhars & Purvadhars, Panchagaon

Kenduli

Banapur

Stories by Arpit

Nayagarh, Bolangir and Boudh Districts

On the western parts of Odisha, sparse presence of Jainism can be seen. Only four

Jain sites have been identified in these three districts. A **broken idol of Shri Parshwanath Bhagwan** can be found lying in ruins at the famous **Harishankar Temple in Balangir**. While many Jain images can be found in **Ranpur** the walls of **Ramnath Temple, Boudh** have images of Jain Tirthankars which indicate that this was a Jain temple earlier.

Jain idols from Nayagarh, Balangir and Boudh Districts

Puri District

Apart from the **Jagannath temple at Puri** where **2 Jain idols** can be found on the **outer walls**, Jain remains can be found in **Barala, Beguniapada, Pindola, Lataharan** among others. At **Jiolo Sasana**, an idol of **Ambika** with a **Tirthankar** is worshipped as **Bhagvati**.

Stories by Arpit JAIN IMAGES FROM PURI DISTRICT

Beguniapada

Barala

District Museum, Puri

Pindola

Lataharan

Ambika with Tirthankar, Jiolo Sasana

Stories by Arpit

Koraput & Rayagada Districts

With the **highest number of Jain historical remains**, **Koraput** in the southern part of Odisha, which shares its borders with Andhra Pradesh and Chhattisgarh, **has 31 Jain sites** while Rayagada has one Jain historical site. **Subei** a village 16 Kms from Sunabeda and 34 Kms away from Koraput has the relics of a Jain temple, containing rare images of the Tirthankars. Other important sites include **Kachela**, **Jamunda**, **Jeypore** among others. Recent excavations in **Biripada** village in Rayagada has revealed various metal idols dating back to the 9th century AD. Further excavations are expected to reveal more such places in future.

Stories by Arpit JAIN IMAGES FROM SUBEI, KORAPUT DISTRICT

Jain images and temples at Subei, Koraput

Stories by Arpit

Jain idols and temples at Subei, Koraput

Stories by Arpit JAIN IMAGES FROM KORAPUT DISTRICT

Kachela, Koraput

B. Singhpur, Koraput

Boriguma

Jamunda, Koraput

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Jain idols from Koraput District

Stories by Arpit JAIN IMAGES FROM KORAPUT DISTRICT

Bhagvati Temple, Jeypore - Chakreshvari Devi worshipped as Bhagvati

Kamata

Jeypore District Museum

Charmula

Phupugaon

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Jain idols from Koraput District

Stories by Arpit JAIN IMAGES FROM KORAPUT DISTRICT

Phampuni

Umbel

Erenga, Jalalput

Deorli, Kotpad

Narayanpal Bastar

Deva Honjor

Chatua

Konga

Godh Bodra

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Jain idols from Koraput District

Jain idols from Koraput&Raygada Districts

The entire list of 123 cities/ towns/ villages in Odisha with Jain heritage sites is as below-

Sl.	City/ Village	District	Location of Jain historical remains
1	Baripada	Mayurbhanj	1. Jagannath Temple 2. Baripada District Museum
2	Khiching	Mayurbhanj	1. MaaKichakeswari Temple Khiching 2. Khiching Museum
3	Badasahi	Mayurbhanj	Ruins of Jain Chaturmukhi Shrine
4	Podasingidi	Keonjhar	1. Jain Heritage Sculpture Shed, ASI 2. Ramachandi Temple
5	Ghasipur/ Chasipur	Keonjhar	Jaina Sculpture Shed , ASI
6	Anandapur	Keonjhar	Baula hill ranges - Yogichhata Temple
7	Bancho	Keonjhar	Unknown
8	Ada	Balasore	Narayan Mandir, Ada
9	Ajodhya	Balasore	Archaeological shed - State Archaeology Dept
10	Puruna	Balasore	Baneshvar Temple, Puruna
11	Bhimpur	Balasore	Private collection of BaikunthNath Dey
12	Balighat	Balasore	Kali Mandir, Balighat
13	Kabara	Balasore	1. Bhramanidevi Shrine 2. Barakhanda Temple

14	Balasure	Balasure	1. Biswanatha Temple Complex 2. GadaChandi Temple
15	Kansa	Balasure	Gramdevti Shrine
16	Majhikia	Balasure	Viswesvaraya Temple, Majhikia
17	Nilagiri	Balasure	Mandalshri Shrine, Nilagiri
18	Jaleswar	Balasure	1. Martasol 2. Panchaghanta 3. Sasanbard
19	Basta	Balasure	Unknown
20	Bardhanpur	Balasure	Unknown
21	Pundal	Balasure	Unknown
22	Kupari	Balasure	Unknown
23	Gundel	Balasure	Unknown
24	Khadipada	Bhadrak	Kailashesvara Temple, near Khadipada
25	Charampa	Bhadrak	1. Odisha State Museum, Bhubaneswar 2. Image of Parshwanath converted into KharakhiaThakurani art Charampa
26	Kushan Nagar	Bhadrak	Worshipped as local deity
27	Jajpur	Jajpur	Hamsesvara Temple
28	Baruadi	Jajpur	1. Chandi Devi Temple 2. Hatkesvara Temple
29	Sitalesvara	Jajpur	1. BasuleiThakurani Temple 2. Jatesvara Temple 3. Sitalesvara Temple
30	Narayana Chowk	Jajpur	Parsvanatha worshipped as Ananta Vasudev
31	DasasvamedhGhat	Jajpur	Ganesh Temple
32	Sana Bazar	Jajpur	Dharmesvara Temple
33	Narasinghpur	Jajpur	Unknown
34	Kartar	Jajpur	Jagulei Shrine
35	Chandigola	Jajpur	Chandesvara Temple
36	Shoradiha	Jajpur	Phalesvara Temple
37	Hatadiha	Jajpur	Jaina Sculpture Shed
38	Kantabania	Jajpur	Barunei Temple
39	Bansabadi	Jajpur	JaguleiGramadevati Temple
40	Taranga Sagarpur	Jajpur	Unknown
41	Champeipal	Jajpur	BudhiJagulei Shrine
42	Sripura	Jajpur	Bhandesvara Temple
43	Kuansa	Jajpur	Mangala Temple
44	Tentulidiha	Jajpur	Unknown
45	Madhupur	Jajpur	Jagannath Temple
46	Naguan	Jajpur	1. Brahmanidevi Temple 2. Shiva Temple 3. Gramdevati Shrine
47	Ratnagiri	Jajpur	Unknown
48	KamudeiPitha	Jajpur	Unknown

49	Nayagarh	Jajpur	Multiple chaturmukhas scattered in fields
50	Kuanrapur	Kendrapara	Harishankareshwara Temple
51	Cuttack	Cuttack	Digambar Jain temple, Choudhury Bazar
52	Baidyesvara	Cuttack	Dhabalesvar Temple, Baidyesvara
53	Pratapnagari	Cuttack	Jain Heritage Museum
54	Bhanapur	Cuttack	ParshwanathBhagwan worshipped as Anantavasudeva, Anantavasudeva Temple, Bhanapur
55	Lendura-Bhagawanpura,	Cuttack	Chaturmukhi Shrine
56	Choudwar	Cuttack	1. Siva Temple, Servants of India Society. Rushabdevprabhu idol completely converted into Shiva idol 2. Ward No. 4 3. MathaSahi 4. Kapaleshwara Temple 5. Bharandi 6. Radhabhallava Temple 7. Chitresvara Temple
57	Athagarh	Cuttack	Tirthankar image carved out of natural laterite bed
58	Kantola	Cuttack	Adyashakti Temple
59	Adaspur	Cuttack	1. Swapnesvara Temple, 2. Nilkantheshwar Temple
60	Mahatabpari	Cuttack	RushiThakurani Shrine
61	Nibharan	Cuttack	Gramesvara Temple
62	Niali	Cuttack	Sobhanesvara Temple
63	Nuadhana	Jagatsinghpur	1. Kapilesvara Temple 2. Archaeological mound 3. Gramdevati Shrine
64	Sahada	Jagatsinghpur	Subamesvara Temple
65	Nasik	Jagatsinghpur	Khandeswara Temple
66	Manapur-Gadhama	Jagatsinghpur	Unknown
67	Kundeswar	Jagatsinghpur	Gatesvara Temple
68	Anla	Jagatsinghpur	Sola PuaMaa Temple
69	Udaygiri Hill	Khordha	Caves under ASI
70	Khandgiri Hill	Khordha	Caves under ASI Digambar Jain temple
71	Bhuvaneshwar	Khordha	1. Orissa State Museum 2. Brahmesvara Temple
72	Sisupalgarh	Khordha	Ruined Temple
73	Jaipurpatana	Khordha	Nistaruni Temple
74	Sunderpada	Khordha	Kalia-Sani Gramadevati Shrine
75	Jamukoli	Khordha	Baghei Devi Temple
76	Panchagaon	Khordha	Jaina Sculpture Shed
77	Banapur	Khordha	Daksha-Prajapati Temple

78	Budhapada	Khordha	Somanath Temple
79	Bagalpur	Khordha	Jaina Sculpture Shed
80	Kenduli	Khordha	1. BaruneiGramadevati Shrine 2. Jajnesvari Temple
81	Ranpur	Nayagarh	Svapnesvara Temple
82	Gobindpur	Nayagarh	Kaunri Devi Temple
83	Gandhamardhan hills	Bolangir	Harishankar Temple, Balangir
84	Boudh	Boudh	Ramnatha Temple Complex
85	Puri	Puri	1. Jagganath Temple 2. Puri District Museum
86	JioloSasana	Puri	Bhagavati Temple. Ambika with NeminathBhagwan worshipped as Bhagavati
87	Pindola	Puri	Bageswari Temple
88	Beguniapada	Puri	Amrutesvara Temple
89	Barala	Puri	Balunkesvara Temple
90	Lataharan	Puri	Unknown
91	Naiguan	Puri	Ambikei Shrine, PurunaOsian
92	Subei	Koraput	Jain Temples
93	Kachela	Koraput	Jain Temple ruins
94	B.Singhpur	Koraput	1. Sankulei Shrine 2. Sculpture Shed
95	Boriguma	Koraput	Bhairav Temple
96	Jamunda	Koraput	Jaina Sculpture Shed
97	Kamata	Koraput	Unknown
98	Charmula	Koraput	Unknown
99	Jeypore	Koraput	1. Bhagwati Temple 2. Gangadei Temple 3. Kali Temple 4. Jeypore District Museum
100	Phupugaon	Koraput	Phupugaon, Kundra
101	Phampuni	Koraput	Unknown
102	Kenduguda	Koraput	Unknown
103	Umbel	Koraput	Unknown
104	Konga	Koraput	Jain Temple
105	Paliva	Koraput	Jain Temple ruins
106	Chatua	Koraput	Chatua, Nandapur
107	Goriahandi	Koraput	Goriahandi, Kundra
108	Erenga	Koraput	Erenga, Jalaput
109	Kashipur	Koraput	Kashipur, Rayagada
110	Deorli	Koraput	Deorli, Kotpad
111	Deva Honjor	Koraput	Deva Honjor, Nandapur
112	Umerkote	Koraput	BhadrasilaPadara
113	Chikima Cave	Koraput	Chikima cave, Jeypore block
114	NarayanpalBastar	Koraput	Unknown

115	Banamaliput	Koraput	Banamaliput, Nandapur
116	GadhBodra	Koraput	GadhBodra, Bastar
117	Injanpur	Koraput	Unknown
118	Padua	Koraput	Unknown
119	Bhairabsinghpur	Koraput	Unknown
120	Kotpad	Koraput	Unknown
121	Charmula	Koraput	Unknown
122	JhodraPoraja Village	Koraput	JainaNisadhi
123	Biripada	Rayagada	Archaeological Mound

References:

- [1] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 503
- [2] Lord Mahavira and his Times by Dr. Kailash Chand Jain, Pg. 16, 69,
- [3] Shodhaganga – Jaina Order, A continuity through adverse economic condition; Pg. 38
- [4] Lord Mahavira and his Times by Dr. Kailash Chand Jain, Pg. 54
- [5] Shodhaganga – Jaina Order, A continuity through adverse economic condition Pg. 39
- [6] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 504
- [7] Muni Speaks – Medium.com (MahameghavahanBhikshurajKharvel by KJ based on “Jain Itihaas” by ParamPujya Acharya Shri Kulchandra Suri.)
- [8] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 504-505;
- [9] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 505
- [10] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 504
- [11] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 505
- [12] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 505
- [13] SailendraNath Sen (1999). Ancient Indian History and Civilization. Pg. 176–177
- [14] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 505
- [15] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 505
- [16] EpigraphiaIndica, Vol. XX (1929–30). Delhi: Manager of Publications, Reprinted 1983.
- [17] HimavantSthaviravali - Pg. 5-8
- [18] Muni Nyayvijayji, Jain Tirtho no Itihas Pg. 560
- [19] Maharaja Kharvel by Acharya Purnachandrasuri Pg. 107-115; Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 505
- [20] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 506;
- [21] Muni Speaks – Medium.com (MahameghavahanBhikshurajKharvel by KJ based on “Jain Itihaas” by ParamPujya Acharya Shri Kulchandra Suri.)
- [22] Jain TirthSarvaSangrah, Sheth AnandjiKalyanjiPedhi, Part II - Pg. 506
- [23] EpigraphiaIndica, Vol. XX (1929–30). Delhi: Manager of Publications, Reprinted 1983

- [24] RadhakumudMookerji (1995). Asoka. Pg. 206.
- [25] AL Basham (1951). History and Doctrines of the Ajivikas, a Vanished Indian Religion. Pg. 158–159
- [26] RomilaThapar (2003). The Penguin History of Early India: From the Origins to AD 1300. Pg. 211–213;
- [27] Helmuth von Glasenapp (1999). Jainism: An Indian Religion of Salvation. Pg. 431;
- [28] <http://www.sdstate.edu/projectsouthasia/upload/HathigumphaInscription.pdf>
- [29] <http://www.sdstate.edu/projectsouthasia/upload/HathigumphaInscription.pdf>
- [30] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Minor_Inscriptions_of_Kharavela
- [31] EpigraphiaIndica, Vol. XX (1929–30). Delhi: Manager of Publications, Reprinted 1983
- [32] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Udayagiri_and_Khandagiri_Caves
- [33] Glory of Jainism: Shri Vajraswami by Dr.Kumarpal Desai (HereNow4U.net)
- [34] Muni Nyayvijayji, Jain Tirtho no Itihas Pg. 560
- [35] N.K.Sahoo, Op.cit Pg. 427-28
- [36] Dr.D.N.Das The early History of Kalinga, Pg-284
- [37] A.S.Altekar, J.N.S.I., Vol. XII, Pg.1-4
- [38] N.K.Sahoo, History of Orissa, Vol.I, Pg.451
- [39] S.N.Rajguru O.H.R.J, 1970
- [40] S, Beal, Budhist Records, Vol. - II, Pg. 208
- [41] T.Watters, on Yan Chwang's Travell in India, Vol.II, Pg. 194-196
- [42] Shodhaganga – Jaina Order, A continuity through adverse economic condition Pg.44
- [43] EpigraphiaIndica, Vol.XXIX, Pg. 38-43
- [44] Shodhaganga – Jaina Order, A continuity through adverse economic condition Pg.46-47
- [45] R.D.Banarji, EpigraphiaIndica, Vol.XIII, Pg.-165ff;
- [46] K.C.Panigrahi, C.B.K.S.O, PP. 52ff
- [47] S.I.I, Vol.X, No.710, V.Rangacharya; A Tropographical list of the Inscriptions of the Madras Presidency, Vol.III, Part.II, PP.316-17, lines 7,13,18and 19
- [48] http://14.139.116.20:8080/jspui/bitstream/10603/281010/19/19_list%20of%20tables%20figures%20plates.pdf
- [49] Dipsikha Acharya, Puravritta -Journal of the Directorate of Archaeology & Museums, Volume 2, 2017, Govt. of West Bengal. Pg. 111-128
- [50] Das Kornel&GiridharGamang, Jaina Antiquities and monuments in Koraput, 2017